

PRODIGEES

Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development

D4.5 Concept for Transnational Open Access Trainings, Implementation and Activity Reports

Project Acronym	PRODIGEES
Project Title	<i>Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development</i>
Grant Agreement No.	873119
Deliverable Reference Number	D4.5
Work Package	4
Deliverable Title	Concept for Transnational Open Access Trainings, Implementation and Activity Reports
Dissemination Level	Public
Deliverable Editor(s)	Wulf Reiners
Author(s)	Benjamin Stewart, Wulf Reiners
Version	1.1
Date	30 August 2024

Transnational Open Access Training (TOAT) Concept

1. Background

Investments in digitalisation affect personal, political, societal, environmental and economic processes across the globe and have enormous potential to radically change almost all sectors in the coming decades, from agriculture to industry and finance, from education to health, democracy and human rights. Digitalisation also influences the success of the worldwide transformation towards sustainable development, as endorsed by the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (UN 2015). Digital technologies are understood to belong to the most powerful facilitators for the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (ITU 2017). At the same time, the digital transformation will only be successful if it is socially accepted and fosters

sustainable and equitable growth. Understanding and shaping the interdependencies between digitalisation and sustainability belongs to the key challenges of the digital era. They are the precondition to employ the transformative potentials of digitalisation to meet the needs and aspirations of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs within the planet's physical boundaries (European Commission 2017).

With the aims to exploit research and innovation results for capacity-development and disseminate generated knowledge to students and trainers, to support the development of digital competencies, and to contribute to cross-cultural understanding, the project 'Promoting Research on Digitalisation in Emerging Powers and Europe Towards Sustainable Development' (PRODIGEES) offers Transnational Open Access Trainings (TOAT) on digitalisation and sustainable development for its research focus areas, Governance and Society, and Economy and Environment.

2. Concept

The TOAT is a three to five-day, hybrid training programme dedicated to dynamic engagement with multi-sectoral, international stakeholders. The aim is to combine the exchange of participants' own perspectives with input and discussions with experts from different sectors and disciplines, as well as from art. Learning and study methods include pre-class preparatory reading, hands-on training on social media use, interactive discussions with experts and decision-makers, group work, as well as the study of applied examples from art. The module thereby covers central issue areas of sustainable development affected by digitalisation, including governance, labour or education, and provides the space to critically discuss related political and societal questions. By contrasting different approaches to the field under scrutiny, the module helps understand the opportunities and risks of technical advances and facilitate visionary thinking about the utilisation of the transformative force of digitalisation for sustainable development. At the end of the TOAT, participants will have gained the following knowledge and skills. They will be able to...

- identify, describe and interpret digitalisation developments in different fields of relevance for the 2030 agenda,
- analyse, critically discuss and assess the opportunities, challenges and limitations of digitalisation with a view to strengthening sustainable development in selected issue areas,
- relate the knowledge on digitalisation to discourses in their home countries and contrast own perspectives with views and experiences from other world regions,
- better use social media for own communicative purposes,
- envision the practical application of digital tools in the professional work context.

This concept provides guidance on the structure of the training along with information on technical preconditions and solutions. The concept shall ensure that the training can be easily replicated in different contexts. As open access content, the concept is free for use by external institutions.

The Training is designed for 20-25 international participants from Emerging Powers (Brazil, China, India, Indonesia, Mexico, and South Africa) and the EU to foster dialogue and network cooperation on key topics in digitalisation and sustainable development. Participants come from government institutions, academia, civil society and business. It is designed as a hybrid format to combine traditional face-to-face classroom with virtual elements. A flipped classroom model foresees the use of PRODIGEES' Digital Knowledge Products, the project's R&I publications, as well as further virtual learning material stored in the PRODIGEES Zenodo open access repository for students to prepare for the lesson content according to their needs and learning styles. Synchronous virtual learning environments allow transnational, in-depth discussions and enable participants to interact directly, thereby contributing to cross-cultural understanding.

3. Preparations

3.1. Call for Applications

The TOAT begins with a Call for Applications, which is disseminated widely in professional networks in Emerging Powers (Brazil, China, India, Indonesia, Mexico, and South Africa) and the EU. Due to their size, economic weight, demographics, and ambitions to shape regional and global affairs, these countries play significant roles in shaping both global sustainable development and digitalisation.

The PRODIGEES project circulated the call among consortium partners, and expanded the call to bigger existing networks, in particular the 'Managing Global Governance' (MGG) network. MGG brings together governmental institutions, think tanks and research institutions as well as civil society and business organizations from Brazil, China, India, Indonesia, Mexico and South Africa as well as Germany and the EU. As an innovative platform for learning and networking with partnerships working at eye-level, employing MGG's communication channels allowed for targeted circulation of the call.

3.2. Composition of Participants

The TOAT is designed for a group of 20-25 participants, which are selected from the group of applicants. The composition of the participants must strike a balance between those in government institutions, think tanks and research institutions, civil society, and the private sector. Government institutions contribute regulatory insights and policy frameworks, think tanks and research institutions provide in-depth analysis and innovation, civil society ensures societal needs and

ethical considerations are addressed, and private sector involvement brings practical solutions, scalability, and market-driven innovation. Thus, multi-stakeholder collaboration enriches the project with a wide range of perspectives, expertise, and resources, allowing for more comprehensive approaches to problem-solving and policy-making.

Participants must be selected for both gender balance and a nearly equal distribution of nationalities. Gender balance ensures diverse perspectives and promotes equity and fairness, offering equal opportunities for all genders, and reflects the diverse needs of society. Similarly, a fair distribution of nationalities ensures a plurality of voices are heard and a diversity of perspectives are applied for solving global, regional, national, and local problems. To combine professional expertise and career potential, participants should have at least 3-5 years of work experience and are typically between 25 and 40 years old. This selection criterion is important because this group typically represents early- to mid-career professionals who are at pivotal points in their careers. They should be highly motivated, and bear potential to become future leaders.

4. Training Programme

4.1. Structure of the Training

The training consists of an online preparatory phase (Module 1) and a focused 5-day programme in person (Module 2-5) dealing with priority areas of the intersection of digitalisation and sustainable development. It closes with a reflection and evaluation part (Module 6).

Module 1: Online Preparation

Module 2: Introduction to Digitalisation and Sustainable Development

Module 3: Data Economy, Disinformation, Privacy, Security, and Surveillance

Module 4: Artificial Intelligence and Automation

Module 5: Digital Rights and Inclusive Digitalisation

Module 6: Reflection and Evaluation

For shorter or longer programmes, fewer or additional priority areas can be considered, including Cyber Security or Global Governance of Digitalisation.

4.2. Tools and Platforms

The training foresees the combination of different meeting and online collaboration tools during the preparatory, implementation, and evaluation phase of the TOAT. The following solutions can be employed:

- [Alchemer](#): For conducting surveys and questionnaires.
- [Microsoft Teams](#) and/or [Zoom](#): For virtual meetings and collaboration, webinars and large group sessions.
- [Miro](#): For interactive workshops and collaborative exercises.
- [Zenodo](#): Open Access Online Repository with Digital Knowledge Products and relevant publications from the PRODIGEES project and beyond.
- [Articulate360](#)'s Rise: The central information hub and participant guide.

The Rise online course-builder plays a central role in all phases of the programme. Rise enables the creation of interactive courses for online access so that participants can engage with content while in different time zones during their preparation for the course, or the follow-up. Information on participation conditions, access to preparatory reading material, and links to external sources or the preparatory online questionnaire can be shared. During the presence phase, the Rise course can be used as a central information hub for further aspects of the programme, including daily information on speakers and reading material or logistical information. In the follow-up phase, participants can access presentation slides and the evaluation tool.

A Rise course can be used repeatedly across different training, making it a cost-effective tool for continuous training and easily updatable.

4.3. Description of Training Modules

The TOAT is structured into modules, each focusing on different aspects of digitalisation. The modules combine mediated and unmediated, synchronous and asynchronous work, leveraging a mix of interactive workshops, expert lectures, group discussions, and practical assignments.

4.3.1. Module 1: Online Preparation

The first module is accomplished by participants asynchronously ahead of the in-person phase. It takes the form of a Rise course that contains practical information on the training participation requirements, an introduction to the agenda and core elements of the training, as well as a reading and watch list for key publications and videos (see resources). The Online Preparation Module also contains a questionnaire that is to be completed by participants. It is created using the Alchemer online survey-making software and serves the purpose to start the thought process of

the participants. The purposes of the questionnaire are 1) to take a survey of the participants' knowledge of and previous engagement with the topic; and 2) familiarize the participants with the themes that will be covered in the Training. The survey is then reviewed in the final module on Reflection and Evaluation. Contrasting answers collected prior to the training with opinions after the course also help reflect acquired knowledge of the topics. The Questionnaire is structured by short answer and scaled questions. The following are example questions from the TOAT:

- *Country (selection from a drop-down menu)*
- *Let's start with a quick brainstorming. What do you understand by digitalisation? What does it mean to you, what examples come to your mind? (short answer)*
- *What are the top 3 hot topics in the public discussion on digitalisation in your country? (one word/phrase per entry)*
- *What does digitalisation mean in your professional life? What is digitised/digitalised? What recent changes have taken place? (short answer)*
- *Do you agree or disagree? Please tick boxes according to your opinion. (scaled)*
- *How do you envision the role of artificial intelligence (AI) in the future, and how could it contribute to sustainable development? (short answer)*
- *What question related to digitalisation would you like to ask a colleague in another country / region? (one entry per represented country/region)*

	Fully disagree	Rather disagree	Rather agree	Fully agree	I don't know
Digitalisation leads to better education	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Digitalisation reduces social inequality	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Digital channels of communication lead to better international exchange	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I feel comfortable to take decisions on the basis of a recommendation generated by an algorithm	<input type="checkbox"/>				
My personal digital data is safe	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I don't mind sharing my data in return for tailor-made offers and benefits	<input type="checkbox"/>				
My digital life adds to my life quality	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I want that an external party constantly monitors my health status	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Fusing human and machine components will create better beings	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Decisions on the basis of digital data are more just	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I don't mind sharing my data to make my digital devices smarter	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I am not concerned that digital technologies (i.e. AI or other) will replace my job	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Digitalisation enhances democratic processes	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Digitalisation is good for the environment	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Google or Tencent knows me better than my loved-ones	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I have a clear understanding of what digitalisation means	<input type="checkbox"/>				

Figure 1 TOAT Introductory Questionnaire, example of scaled questions

Reviewing the results prior to the beginning of Module 2 also helps training facilitators to get a feeling for the knowledge of the participants and existing perceptions and opinions on central questions and problems at the intersection of digitalisation and sustainable development.

4.3.2. Module 2: Introduction to Digitalisation and Sustainable Development

Module 2 establishes a foundational understanding of how digitalisation intersects with global sustainability goals. This introduction sets the stage for participants by contextualizing the broader implications of digitalisation, ensuring that subsequent discussions are grounded in the challenges and opportunities of integrating digital technologies with sustainable development. It also aligns all participants with a shared knowledge base, facilitating more effective and focused learning throughout the course.

Objective: Introduce participants to the fundamental concepts of digitalisation and its relevance to sustainable development and set a common basis of understanding and vocabulary

Activities:

- Welcome and introduction session

- Keynote lecture on the intersection of digitalisation and sustainability
- Group discussion on personal connections to digitalisation
- Interactive session on the impact of smartphones
- Session for participants to present their own background and expertise on the topic
- Introduction of the video assignment

The participants are tasked with a 'video assignment', which requires them, during the Training, to create a 30-second to 2-minute video that highlights a digitalisation innovation in their locality, be it the workplace, community, or home. The assignment encourages participants to reflect upon how digitalisation already affects and is integrated into their professional and personal lives.

4.3.3. Module 3: Data Economy, Disinformation, Privacy, Security, and Surveillance

Module 3 addresses the complex ethical and societal implications of digitalisation. This session equips participants with the knowledge to navigate the challenges posed by data-driven technologies, including the risks of disinformation and the need for robust privacy and security measures. By exploring these topics, participants will be better prepared to develop and advocate for policies that protect individual rights while fostering a secure and transparent digital environment.

Objective: Explore the ethical, social, and political dimensions of the data economy, disinformation, privacy, security, and surveillance.

Activities:

- Expert lectures on big data, privacy, and social media ethics
 - Examining impacts and cases of disinformation on democratic elections
 - Group discussions on the local and global impacts of data practices and exploitation
 - Viewing and analysis of relevant documentaries (e.g., "The Cleaners")
- The viewing of any film should be accompanied by the appropriate trigger warnings and prior notification of the type of content, especially explicit and graphic content and content showing abuse, violence, and mental health disturbances. Participants must consent to the viewing and are permitted to excuse themselves at any time.*
- Case studies on data breaches and the use of technology in surveillance

4.3.4. Module 4: Artificial Intelligence and Automation

Module 4 explores the transformative impacts of AI on economies, labour markets, and societal structures. This session provides participants with insights into both the opportunities and challenges presented by AI, including ethical considerations and the potential for job displacement.

By exploring these critical issues, participants will be better equipped to shape policies that harness AI's potential while mitigating its risks.

Objective: Understand the implications of artificial intelligence (AI) and automation for the future of work and governance.

Activities:

- Lectures on AI applications in various sectors, including creating a common understanding of ‘what is AI’.
- Fishbowl discussion on the promises and challenges of AI.
Fishbowl discussions are a facilitation technique where a small group of participants engage in a discussion in a central "fishbowl" while others observe, with observers rotating into the discussion, creating a dynamic exchange of ideas. The format is useful to keep everyone in the group engaged through active listening. The roles between ‘expert’ and ‘participant’ become fluid and interchangeable.
- Workshop called, ‘Future of Labour’, with interactive activities and group reflections. The Future of Labour workshop begins with a viewing of the video “Humans Need Not Apply” by CGP Grey (2014). The viewing is followed by a review of the ‘Futures Cone’, a futures-visualisation model by Joseph Voros (2017). Afterwards, participants brainstorm ideal and possible futures, based upon technology’s impact on the economy and society, as shown in the video and as understood by the content of the Training. They propose solutions to a selected problem identified in the present. Then the participants do ‘backcasting’ in order to map the steps necessary from the imagined ideal future to the present day problem.
The goal of this workshop is to investigate the opportunities and challenges of the field and to design solutions for potential future problems. Backcasting is used to identify ideal futures in the context of the problem and then map the conditions necessary from those futures to our present situation. Backcasting is a planning method where participants envision a desired future and work backwards to identify strategies needed to achieve that future, focusing on long-term goals and how to reach them.
- Visit to a relevant exhibition or museum in the location of the training. For example, the [Futurium](#) in Berlin, Germany, is a museum which inspires critical reflection on how technology shapes our present and future.

4.3.5. Module 5: Digital Rights and Inclusive Digitalisation

Module 5 tackles equity and accessibility challenges in the digital era. This session focuses on ensuring that the benefits of digitalisation are distributed fairly, protecting the rights of all individuals, and preventing the digital divide from exacerbating social inequalities. By exploring these issues, participants will be empowered to advocate for inclusive policies that ensure everyone can participate fully in the digital economy.

Objective: Address issues related to digital rights, access, and inclusion in the digital age

Activities:

- Sessions on digital rights and media development
- Workshop on the digital divide and strategies for inclusive digitalisation
- Group activities to brainstorm solutions for digital inclusion
- Discussions on equality and fragmentation in the digital space

4.3.6. Module 6: Reflection and Evaluation

Module 6 translates theoretical knowledge into actionable strategies. This session allows participants to identify how to apply what they have learned in real-world scenarios, fostering a deeper understanding of how to implement digitalisation initiatives effectively. Reflection on these applications ensures that participants can critically assess their approaches, refine their strategies, and prepare to tackle future challenges with confidence.

Objective: Facilitate the practical application of knowledge and skills acquired during the training and encourage reflective thinking.

Activities:

- Reflective exercises on learning outcomes and future applications building on the results of the questionnaire completed ahead of the training (see Module 1)
The reflective exercises are pre-empted by a review of the original questionnaire that participants were required to fill out at the beginning of the training. By reviewing the questionnaire, trainers and participants identify trends. Then the trainers ask participants to reflect on if and how their understandings of the topics changed since taking the survey.
- Submission and presentation of video assignments showcasing local digitalisation impacts (see Module 2)
- Journaling and individual reflections on the training experience
Journaling exercises invite participants to write individually about their thoughts, experiences, and learning processes, fostering deeper reflection, personal insight, and self-assessment of their growth over time. Questions to provoke critical reflection about the topic could include:
 - *What is sustainable digitalisation, and what is digital sustainability?*
 - *If you had access to all data in the world, which sustainability problem would you address (and how)?*
 - *Did you experience a utopian or a dystopian ‘moment’ during the training?*
- Evaluation and feedback session to gather participants’ insights and suggestions

The Evaluation Survey serves to gather feedback on the course's effectiveness, allowing instructors to assess whether learning objectives were met and identify areas for improvement. It helps measure participant satisfaction, content relevance, and the overall impact of the Training. Additionally, the survey provides valuable insights for future iterations of the course, ensuring continuous improvement and alignment with participants' evolving needs. The Evaluation Survey is structured in scaled questions and short answer questions. The scaled questions assess each element of the TOAT's a) content, b) learning process, c) speakers and facilitators, and d) structure, methods, and materials. The short answer questions provide a space for open feedback on positive aspects of the programme, areas for improvement, and general feedback. Possible evaluation questions include (six-step scale from 'totally agree' to 'strongly disagree'):

- *The training enabled me to better understand the interconnection of sustainable development and digitalisation*
- *The training addressed the most relevant areas of digitalisation*
- *The training enables me to contrast own digitalisation experiences and perspectives with views and experiences from other world regions.*
- *The training enabled me to contrast own digitalisation experiences and perspectives with views and experiences from other world regions.*
- *The training enabled me to envision the use of digital technologies in my professional work context.*
- *The dialogue and learning atmosphere was good and productive.*
- *There was enough time for discussion and interaction.*
- *There were sufficient opportunities for own contributions to the debates.*
- *I could develop problem-solving competences relevant for my professional life.*
- *I am satisfied with my learning process.*
- *The training was well structured.*
- *There was a good mix of theory and practice-orientation.*
- *There was a good balance between input and discussions.*
- *The facilitation material (RISE, presentations, questionnaire, instructions, etc.) provided good guidance through the process.*
- *There were sufficient time and opportunities for informal exchange and networking.*

Another six-step scale from 'very good' to 'very poor' is used to assess the participants' reception of each activity, presentation, and discussion in each Module of the Training. A short-answer section for open feedback allows for participants to elaborate by asking questions such as:

- *What did you like in particular (regarding content, learning process, speakers, structure/methods/material or other aspects)? What should we definitively keep in the programme next year?*
- *What can we improve (regarding content, learning process, speakers, structure/methods/material or other aspects)? What alternative elements would you suggest to include in the programme?*
- *Do you have any other feedback for us regarding the training?*

5. Resources

5.1. Literature

Anbumozhi, V., Babu, S., Bollino, C. A., Diyanah, S. M., Hanifah, V. W., Hidayat, S., Kozono, M., Kumar, A., Nugroho, A. E., Permani, R., Sahara, S., Syukur, M. & Wardhana, I. W. (2022). [Digital transformation of agri-food system: policy pathways for greater socio-economic inclusion, sustainability, and international cooperation.](#) Jakarta: G20 Insights.

Bilotta, N. (2022). [Can digital currencies end financial exclusion in Indonesia? Economic realities and policy ambitions.](#) IAI Papers 22|24. Rome: Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI).

Breuer, A. (2024). [Information integrity and information pollution. Vulnerabilities and impact on social cohesion and democracy in Mexico.](#) IDOS Discussion Paper 2/2024. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).

Čas, J. (2023). [„Künstliche Intelligenz“ und soziale Nachhaltigkeit. Ethische Prinzipien für KI-Technologien als Lösungen für die Reduktion von Armut und Ungleichheit.](#) *Magazin erwachsenenbildung.at. Das Fachmedium für Forschung, Praxis und Diskurs* 49.

Crawford, K. (2021). *Atlas of AI: Power, Politics, and the Planetary Costs of Artificial Intelligence.* Yale University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00287-021-01385-5>

Colantoni, L. & Sangiorgio, A. (2024). [Agriculture and deforestation. How to reduce the impact of the EU's agricultural imports on global forests.](#) Rome: Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI).

Colantoni, L. (2023). [Technologies to protect global forests: the case of Indonesia.](#) *IAI Commentaries* 23(59), 1-6. Rome: Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI).

Dang, V., Lynders, E. & Reiners, W. (2023). [Big ambition meets geopolitics. Are Southern voices and the SDGs the way to success for India's G20 presidency?](#) *The Current Column* 21 August 2023. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).

Dang, V., Bootwalla, A., Lynders, E. M. & Reiners, W. (2024). [Synergising digital public infrastructure and digital commons for sustainable development](#). Mumbai: Gateway House: Indian Council on Global Relations.

European Commission (2017a): Commission Staff Working Document Digital4Development: mainstreaming digital technologies and services into EU Development Policy. SWD(2017) 157, https://ec.europa.eu/europeaid/sites/devco/files/swd-digital4development_part1_v3.pdf.

European Commission (2017b): A concept paper on digitisation, employability and inclusiveness - the role of Europe. http://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/document.cfm?doc_id=44515.

European Commission (2017c): Attitudes towards the impact of digitisation and automation on daily life. Special Eurobarometer 460, March 2017, doi:10.2759/835661.

German Advisory Council on Global Change (WBGU). (2019). *Towards Our Common Digital Future Flagship Report*.

Grimm, S., & Klingebiel, S. (Eds.) (2024). *Transnational cooperation - an explorative collection* (IDOS Discussion Paper). <https://doi.org/10.23661/idp4.2024>

Grimm, S., Plasencia Díaz, A., & Alves, P. (Eds.). (2022). *Training civil services on the 2030 Agenda: Skills development for working towards the common good*. Escola Nacional de Administração Pública (ENAP).

Haegele, R. & Mansur, J. A. (2023). [Women, Water, Wi-Fi. How digitalisation and technology empower women working on the ocean and along the Amazon River](#). *The Current Column* 19 June 2023. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).

Hassan, R. (2020). Digitality, Virtual Reality and The ‘Empathy Machine.’ *Digital Journalism*, 8(2), 195–212. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21670811.2018.1517604>

Heuwinkel, S. & Haegele, R. (2024). [Kommunikation in der Polykrise. Was Wissenschaftskommunikation von konstruktivem Journalismus lernen kann](#). *The Current Column* 27 March 2024. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).

International Telecommunication Union (2017): Buenos Aires Declaration. Buenos Aires: World Telecommunication Development Conference (WTDC-17), 9-20 October 2017.

Kachelmann, M. & Reiners, W. (2023). The European Union’s governance approach to tackling disinformation – protection of democracy, foreign influence, and the quest for digital sovereignty. *L’Europe en Formation* 396(2), 11-36. <https://doi.org/10.3917/eufor.396.0011>

Kumar A. (2023). [Digitalisation for inclusive development: an overview of digital strategies and public policies in the Europe and India](#). RIS Discussion Paper Series 280. New Delhi: Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS).

Lanier, J. (2017). Chapter 4: Why I love VR. *Dawn of the New Everything : encounters with reality and virtual reality*. Henry Holt and Company.

Lucatello, S., & Leconte, A. (2021). [Complex Systems, fragility and security: challenges for the EU governance and its global partners in climate change and digitalization](#). *L'Europe en formation* 393(2), 188-205.

Lucatello, S., & Reiners, W. (2024): [Can we bring digitalisation and the environment together? Agenda and coalitions beyond techno-fix illusions](#). *The Current Column* 13 February 2024. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).

Lucatello, S. & Reiners, W. (2024, March 24). [Los costos ambientales de la digitalización](#). *El Universal*.

Lynders, E. & Reiners, W. (2022, September 14). [A new era for the G20? Insights from the T20 Summit 2022 in Indonesia](#). IDOS Blog.

Reiber, T. & Schwachula, A. (2023). *Enabling transformative policymaking through problem-based learning*. EU-SPRI Conference 2021, [Session: “The use of participatory methods for transformative innovation engagements”](#).

Reiber, T., & Reiners, W. (2019). New educational formats for civil service needed worldwide to support global sustainability. *Diplomatisches Magazin*, 26–29.

Reiners, W. (2021). [Die Digitalisierungsstrategie der Europäischen Union – Meilensteine und Handlungsfelder zwischen digitaler Souveränität und grüner Transformation](#). *integration* 44(4), 266-286.

Sarno, G. S. (2023). [Building climate resilience in urban informal settlements through data co-production](#). *IAI Commentaries* 23(13), 1-6. Rome: Istituto Affari Internazionali (IAI).

Schneider, I. & Srinivas, K. R. (2023, March 14). [A chance for India to shape a data governance regime. The crafting of the country’s data governance must enable a secure, more egalitarian, and trustworthy digital future for all](#). *The Hindu*.

Schneider, I. (2022). [Das ferne Echo Europas: Plattformregulierung, Datenschutz und Digitalkultur in Mexiko](#). In A. Bogner, M. Decker, M. Nentwich & C. Scherz (Eds.), *Digitalisierung und die Zukunft der Demokratie. Beiträge aus der Technikfolgenabschätzung* (pp. 33-46). Baden-Baden: Nomos Verlagsgesellschaft mbH & Co. KG.

Schneider, I. (2018). Bringing the State Back In: Big Data-based capitalism, disruption, and novel regulatory approaches in Europe. In *The Politics and Policies of Big Data Big Data, Big Brother?*. (pp. 129–175). Routledge.

Srinivas, K. R. (2021, April 27). [A European approach to regulate artificial intelligence: possible global impact](#). RIS Blog.

Stewart, B. & Reiners, W. (2022). [How Open Science can revolutionize global knowledge cooperation](#). *The Current Column* 4 November 2022. Bonn: German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS).

Stewart, B. (2023). [A case for open science in Indonesia: advancing digital literacy, scientific infrastructure, and leadership](#). Jakarta: Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS).

The World in 2050 Initiative. (2019). *The Digital Revolution and Sustainable Development : Opportunities and Challenges Report prepared by The World in 2050 initiative*.
<https://doi.org/10.22022/TNT/05-2019.15913>

Toernberg, P. (2022). How digital media drive affective polarization through partisan sorting. *PNAS*, 119(42). <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas>

United Nations General Assembly (2015): Transforming our world: the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. 21 October 2015, A/RES/70/1.

Voros, J. (2017, February 24). *The Futures Cone, use and history*. The Voroscope.
<https://thevoroscope.com/2017/02/24/the-futures-cone-use-and-history/>

5.2. Videos

Bilotta, N. (2022, August 26). [Can digital currencies end financial exclusion in Indonesia? Economic realities and policy ambitions](#)

Block, H., & Rieseewieck, M. (Directors). (2018). *The Cleaners* [Motion picture]. Germany: Kloos & Co. Medien.

Breuer, A. (2023, February 2). [Conversatorio El acceso a la información y la apertura de datos: Beneficios y retos de la digitalización para la sociedad mexicana](#).

Breuer, A. (2024, March 12). [To inform and misinform: the current situation of Brazil's information ecosystem](#). Webinar with Fundação Getulio Vargas (FGV), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

CGP Grey. (2014, August 13). *Humans need not apply* [Video]. YouTube.
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7Pq-S557XQU&t=1s>

Lucatello, S. (2021, January 21). [Climate change and digitalisation: setting the context](#). CIFE Executive Training Webinar, Centre international de formation européenne (CIFE), Nice, France.

Lynders, E. (2022, September 19). [Paradigm shifts in environmental policies: the role of digital communication and knowledge exchange in the T20/G20 transnational policy community.](#)

Lynders, E. & Reiners, W. (2019). *Digitalisation: Transformative effects for sustainable development* [Video]. German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS). YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=onf-82bRhYY>

Rafliana, I. (2022, April 18). [Traveling waves: the Indonesian tsunami warning system](#), BRIN PRW STS Webinar Series #1, Indonesia.

Sarno, G. S. (2022, December 20). [Urban resilience to extreme natural events and climate change: from Brasil to Europe.](#) Workshop with FGV, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

Schneider, I. (2021, November 25). [Convergence and divergence in global data protection law.](#) Panel discussion, King's College London & British Institute of International and Comparative Law (BIICL).

Schneider, I. (2021, October 1). [Can digital platforms be democratically regulated?](#) Webinar with Fundação Getulio Vargas (FGV), Rio de Janeiro, Brazil.

Schneider, I. (2023, January 24). [Digital Sovereignty and data governance in times of geopolitical rivalry.](#) Science, Technology and Innovation Policy (STIP) Forum Lecture Series, Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS), New Delhi, India.

Stewart, B. (2021, November 16). [Open Science: epistemologies, science policy implementation and digitalisation.](#)

Stewart, B. (2023 March 13). [The State of Open Science in Indonesia: a preliminary analysis of digitalisation's impact on science regimes.](#)

TEDx Talks. (2020, November 18). *Sustainability in the digital age* | Dirk Messner | TEDxBonn [Video]. YouTube. <https://youtu.be/VpFgNZSwm-A>

vpro documentary. (2019, December 21). *Shoshana Zuboff on surveillance capitalism* | VPRO Documentary [Video]. YouTube. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hIXhnWUmMvw>

6. Annexes: Activity Reports: TOAT programmes 2020-2023

Annex 1: Transnational Open Access Training programme, 2020 (online)

Annex 2: Transnational Open Access Training programme, 2021 (online)

Annex 3: Transnational Open Access Training programme, 2022 (in-person w/ hybrid elements)

Annex 4: Transnational Open Access Training programme, 2023 (in-person w/ hybrid elements)

Annex 1: Transnational Open Access Training, 2020 Programme

The first TOAT took place fully online from 16-23 October 2020 in collaboration with the MGG Academy, coordinated by the German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS) with representation and support from Instituto Mora (MORA) and the University of Hamburg (UHAM). The Training was comprised of 24 participants from Brazil, China, Germany, India, Indonesia, Mexico, the Netherlands, and South Africa, representing institutions in government, think tanks and research, civil society, and the private sector.

The programme was designed using an online collaborative tool called [Mural](#). In later editions of the TOAT, Miro, a different collaborative software, was adopted as a substitute for Mural.

The programme schedule was designed with the pre-learning elements in the left column, and then the implementation of the Training proceeding through the days represented by each successive column to the right.

Because the Training took place online, instructions and facilitation for participants were separated by Regional Calls accounting for their time zones and availability.

Annex 2: Transnational Open Access Training on Sustainable Digitalisation, 2021 Programme

The second TOAT took place fully online from 13-15 September 2021 in collaboration with the MGG Academy, coordinated by the German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS) with representation and support from Instituto Mora (MORA) and the University of Hamburg (UHAM). The Training was comprised of 24 participants from Brazil, China, Germany, India, Indonesia, Mexico, and South Africa, representing institutions in government, think tanks and research, civil society, and the private sector.

Because the Training took place online, instructions and facilitation for participants were separated by Regional Calls accounting for their time zones and availability. Difference in time zone mandated that some course content be delivered in live online sessions (facilitated work) and some course content be covered by participants independently (unfacilitated work). The schedule is best understood by proceeding through the days (left column), recognizing the delineation between facilitated and unfacilitated work (middle columns) and identifying time of the day's Regional Calls and their content (individual cells).

Facilitated online by Dr. Wulf Reiners and Benjamin Stewart

Schedule

Day	Facilitated work	Unfacilitated work	Background material
<i>Before the module</i>		Participants fill out a Digitalisation Questionnaire	
<i>Monday, 13 Sep 2021</i>	<p>Regional Call East: Dr. Wulf Reiners & Benjamin Stewart (3h), 9:00-12:00 CET (UTC 7-10)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome & Introduction (30 min) Future of Labour Workshop (2h 30 min) <p>Regional Call West: Dr. Wulf Reiners & Benjamin Stewart (3h), 16:30-19:30 CET (UTC 14:30-17:30)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Welcome & Introduction (30 min) 	<p>Group Reflection Exercise West, 18:00-20:00 CET (UTC 16:00-18:00)</p> <p>Participants discuss Professor Ingrid Schneider's pre-recorded video and background material. Posting their reflections onto the Reflection Mural, they answer these questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> What content is familiar? What content is new? Where do I see this content in my country, in my community and in my home? 	<p>Professor Ingrid Schneider's Pre-recorded video</p> <p>Professor Ingrid Schneider's text, "Bringing the State Back in"</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Future of Labour Workshop (2h 30 min) <p>Main Idea: Introduce the video assignment and expose participants to the promises and risks of digitalisation. Encourage problem posing and problem solving skills in the context of imagined digital futures.</p>	<p>Main Idea: Connect old preconceptions of digitalisation with new knowledge. Inspire initial connections between global digital problems and digitalisation’s impact in one’s locality.</p>	
<p>Tuesday, 14 Sep 2021</p>	<p>Regional Call East: Ingrid Schneider on Big data, privacy & security (2h), 9:00 – 11:00 CET (UTC 7:00-9:00)</p> <p>Regional Call West: Ingrid Schneider on Social media & disinformation (2h), 16:30-18:30 CET (UTC 14:30-16:30)</p> <p>Main idea: Give participants a crash course on digitalisation topics with clear global and local impacts. Provide direct access to an expert for in-depth learning.</p>	<p>Group Reflection Exercise East, 6:00-8:00 CET (UTC 4:00-6:00)</p> <p>Participants discuss the content thus far. Posting their reflections on the Reflection Mural, they answer the questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How does the content impact my local community? • How would I like the content to impact my local community? • In my opinion, what are the most important topics in digitalisation that people in my local community should be talking about? <p>Main Idea: Connect old preconceptions of digitalisation with new knowledge. Inspire initial connections between global digital problems and digitalisation’s impact in one’s locality.</p>	<p>Interview (video) with Shoshana Zuboff</p> <p>OR</p> <p>TEDX Bonn, Dirk Messner Video on Digitalisation and Sustainable Futures +</p> <p>One of three other videos (following the video guide for the respective video):</p> <p>Dr. Piali De on Artificial Intelligence in Health Care</p> <p>Patricia Ferrante on Digitalisation in Media and Education</p> <p>Dr. Carlos Dominguez on the Digital Divide</p> <p>Reading selected sections of “Towards our common digital future” by the WBGU</p> <p>OR</p> <p>Reading selected sections of “The Digital Revolution” by The World in 2050</p>
<p>Wednesday, 15 Sep 2021</p>	<p>Prime Time Call: Wulf & Ben (2h), 14:00-16:00 CET (UTC 12:00-14:00)</p>	<p>Submission of Video Assignments</p>	

	<p>We review the Future of Labour Murals, the Reflection Mural and the Digitalisation Questionnaire. Participants reflect upon what they have learned throughout the module.</p> <p>Main idea: Harvest the learnings and reflections of participants. Respond to outstanding concerns, questions and insights.</p>	<p>Main idea: Participants make connections between global digital transformations and impacts on their local community, demonstrating these impacts with short clips of their local environments.</p>	
--	---	---	--

Annex 3: Transnational Open Access Training on Sustainable Digitalisation, Programme 2022

The third TOAT took place in-person in Bonn, Germany with hybrid elements from 17-21 October 2022, in collaboration with the MGG Academy, coordinated by the German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS) with representation and support from Instituto Mora (MORA) and the University of Hamburg (UHAM). The Training was comprised of 24 participants from Brazil, China, Germany, India, Indonesia, Mexico, and South Africa, representing government institutions, think tanks and research, civil society, and private sector.

Sustainable Digitalisation 17 – 21 October

Transnational Open Access Training

Monday, 17 October

9.00 am – 1.00 pm	Introduction: Digitalisation and sustainable development <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr Wulf Reiners & Benjamin Stewart, IDOS
2.30 pm – 4.00 pm	Digital Rights & Media Developments <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Julius Endert, Senior Consultant on Policy and Learning at Digital Sphere, DW Akademie, Bonn
4.30 – 5.00 pm	The VR experiences <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Andrea Robles, MGG alumna, Mexico

Tuesday, 18 October

9.00 am – 4.00 pm with lunch break 12.30 pm – 2 pm	Data economy, privacy, and social media – ethics & politics <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prof Dr Ingrid Schneider, University of Hamburg, Department of Informatics, Ethics in IT
5.00 pm – 7.30 pm	[optional] Movie & Discussion: The Cleaners

Wednesday, 19 October

9.00 – 10.30 am	Artificial Intelligence in the Workplace <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Naira López Canellas, European Digital SME Alliance
11.00 am – 12.30 pm	Fishbowl “Sustainable Digitalisation: Interim Reflection” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Naira López Canellas, European Digital SME Alliance • Prof Dr Ingrid Schneider, University of Hamburg, Department of Informatics, Ethics in IT • Gaurav Sharma, Artificial Intelligence Fellow, Academy of International Affairs NRW
2.30 – 4.00 pm	Visit and kick-start introduction: Exhibition “Mission AI - Artificial Intelligence Experience: Opportunities, Risks and Challenges of the Key Technology of the 21st Century”, Deutsches Museum Bonn

Thursday, 20 October

9.00 – 10.30 am	The digital divide, access and inclusion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr Carlos Dominguez, Instituto Mora, Mexico • Benjamin Stewart, IDOS
11.00 am – 12.30 pm	Equality and fragmentation in the digital space <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Nnenna Nwakanma, World Wide Web Foundation (online)
2.00 – 4.00 pm	Workshop: The future of labour <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr Wulf Reiners & Benjamin Stewart, IDOS

Friday, 21 October

9.00 am – 12.30 pm	Concluding Discussion <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr Wulf Reiners & Benjamin Stewart, IDOS
--------------------	--

Annex 4: Transnational Open Access Training on Sustainable Digitalisation, Programme 2023

The fourth TOAT took place in-person in Berlin, Germany with hybrid elements from 9-13 October 2023, in collaboration with the MGG Academy, coordinated by the German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS) with representation and support from Fundação Getúlio Vargas (FGV), Instituto Mora (MORA), Research and Information System for Developing Countries (RIS), and the University of Hamburg (UHAM). The Training was comprised of 21 participants from Brazil, China, Germany, India, Indonesia, Mexico, Romania, and South Africa, representing institutions in government, think tanks and research, civil society, and the private sector.

Transnational Open Access Training on “Sustainable Digitalisation”

PROGRAMME

9 – 13 October 2023	
Monday, 9 October	<p>11:30-12:30: Sustainable Digitalisation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr Wulf Reiners, IDOS • Benjamin Stewart, IDOS <hr/> <p>14:00-14:30: Environmental Impact of Digitalisation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prof. Dr Simone Lucatello, Instituto Mora <hr/> <p>14:30-16:30: Climate Impact of Digitalisation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Josefine Hintz, TU Berlin
Tuesday, 10 October	<p>9:30-12:30: Data Economy, Privacy and Social Media (Part I)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prof. Dr Ingrid Schneider, University of Hamburg, Department of Informatics, Ethics in IT <hr/> <p>14:00-16:00: Data Economy, Privacy and Social Media (Part II)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prof Dr Ingrid Schneider, University of Hamburg, Department of Informatics, Ethics in IT <hr/> <p>17:00: Movie – <i>The Cleaners</i> (optional) & Discussion</p>

Wednesday, 11 October	<p>9:30-12:30: Inclusive Digitalisation Workshop</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Geraldine de Bastion, Konnektiv • Michael Jensen, Association for Progressive Communication • Titiksha Vashist, Pranava Institute • Kudzai M. Mubaiwa, Digital Innovation Ecosystem Specialist <hr/> <p>14:00-16:00: Future of Labour Workshop</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr Wulf Reiners, IDOS • Benjamin Stewart, IDOS
Thursday, 12 October	<p>9:30-11:00 The Digital Agenda for Global Governance</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • John Reyels, Head of Division Cyber Foreign Policy and Cyber Security Coordination Staff, Federal Foreign Office • Dr Julia Pohle, Berlin Social Science Center <hr/> <p>11:30-12:30: Reflection and Evaluation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dr Georg Witschel, Ambassador (ret.) • Dr Wulf Reiners, IDOS • Benjamin Stewart, IDOS • Matthias Kachelmann, IDOS
Friday, 13 October	<p>12:30-14:30: Farewell Ceremony and Lunch</p>

